

A glance into the boundary lubrication mechanism of PVA hydrogel after the reduction of interstitial fluid pressurization

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Abstract

The present study introduces a tribological comparison of five polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) hydrogel specimens with different physiological properties, a possible candidating materials for cartilage replacement. The superior lubrication of synovial cartilage is believed to lie in solid-to-solid molecular interactions. Therefore, the focus was paid to investigation of boundary lubrication with regards to interstitial fluid flow reduction. The experiments were carried out in ball-on-plate (glass-on-hydrogel) configuration. Based on the experiments we proposed a boundary lubrication mechanism, selected a hydrogel that showed the least surface damage and highlighted the desired properties that should be considered when developing the artificial cartilage.

Keywords

PVA hydrogel, boundary lubrication, biotribology, artificial cartilage, friction

1. Introduction

Synovial cartilage, a vital component facilitating the smooth movement of most living animals, incorporates a superior lubrication mechanism unmatched by manmade bearings. Despite its potential advantages in cost savings, minimal maintenance, and prolonged service life, replicating its performance remains a challenge.

Articular cartilage, is a complex water-based tissue, having structural and molecular differences all the way from its attachment to the subchondral bone to its articulating surface. [1] A major importance in cartilage superior behavior is the superficial layer permeated with molecules (protein, hyaluronic acid, aggrecan, lubricin, phospholipids)

likely giving the crucial aspect of extremely low friction (<0.001) under high loads, while slow movement. [2] Cartilage is primarily composed of collagen fibrils and proteoglycan, with collagen fibers aligned parallelly toward the articular surface and transitioning to a perpendicular orientation towards the deep zones. [3] Such fiber organization preserves the subchondral bone from overloading and articulating surfaces to resist mechanical stresses. [4] Proteoglycan's role is to hold water within the cartilage and contribute to its toughness. Proteoglycans, like aggrecan and lubricin, also contribute to lubrication. [2, 5] Cartilage is easier to deform in a compressive direction than traverse direction, allowing internal fluid to head directly into the contact area during deformation and act as fluid load support. [6, 7] Cartilage dysfunction, such as osteoarthritis (OA), often results from initial damage leading to disrupted lubrication, increased friction, and progressive structural changes. Chondrocytes are believed to play a crucial role in recognizing and responding to pathological changes in cartilage. [2]

Researchers worldwide are proposing various mechanisms for lubrication, yet none ensure crucial low friction under high pressure. While some mechanisms work well under specific conditions, none replicates the effectiveness of natural cartilage lubrication. Mechanisms range from basic hydrodynamic lubrication, well-known from the theory of machine to newer models considering interstitial fluid load support and molecular support. [8–12]

The coefficient of friction (COF) is understood as energy dissipation as two opposing surfaces rub each other. The energy lost to friction is classified as viscous friction and boundary friction. By viscous friction, we mean contactless sliding, where dissipation is lost to fluid viscosity resistance. Boundary friction is considered as intermolecular contact between sliding surfaces and is crucial for superior performance. [13]

A lubricating mechanism concerning viscous friction (fluid film lubrication) is a biphasic model, composed of a porous-permeable matrix and water. Lubrication film between articulating surfaces arises when interstitial fluid is squeezed out from the cartilage under deformation. [10, 14] The majority of the load applied on the cartilage is carried out by the interstitial fluid pressurization and only a small portion is transmitted to solid cartilage. [15] When porous cartilage is not rehydrated, either by unloading (e.g. walking) [16] or by movement [17], the fluid pressurization effect gradually fades away. This is accompanied by an increase in solid-to-solid contact and friction increase [14]. Biphasic lubrication is believed to be the first to act after loading cartilage.

When the fluid film lubrication diminishes and surfaces make molecular contact, understanding the characteristics structures and molecular composition of boundary layers forming at the superficial zone becomes crucial. Unlike fluid flow lubrication, boundary lubrication is largely independent of substrate. [13] Recent studies have revealed that it is not one single molecule standing behind the superior lubrication but rather every one of them has its unique

59 role in either securing the boundary, maintaining it, or acting as a low shear component. [13, 18] Phospholipids (PLs)
60 seem to be particularly crucial for low shear, with some studies reporting friction as low as 0.0001 under load over 150
61 atm, corresponding to conditions in the human body, using PLs attached on mica surface. [19] The lubrication
62 mechanism enabling such performance was termed the hydration lubrication mechanism defined as hydrated molecular
63 heads repulsing other hydrated heads attached to the opposing surface. [20] However, PLs tested with cartilage tissue
64 do not exhibit such performance on their own, likely because of the absence of forming rigid boundaries as at the mica
65 surface. HA seems to play an important effect in securing the weak boundary, due to its ability to better adsorb at the
66 surface and interlink with other molecules, such as PLs. An important role in preserving low friction at close contact are
67 proteins (albumin and γ -globulin) forming at the top of the boundary layer and protecting the underlying layers from
68 wear. Protein forms a laminated film of durable γ -globulin and easy shear albumin layer. [13, 21, 22] Importantly, the
69 inappropriate concentration of lubricant components affects the overall performance greatly. Too high albumin content
70 may lead to peeling of the boundary layer [23]. If PLs concentration is high, the desired distribution of liposomes will
71 not occur, leading to excessive wear. However appropriate concentration of components in lubricant could substantially
72 reduce friction and wear. [24]

73 The boundary layer might be divided into two zones, an adsorbed film and a gel-like layer. [25] The adsorbed
74 film, primarily composed of synovia constituents, is expected to come first into contact when biphasic lubrication
75 appears ineffective under given conditions. The gel-like film underlying the adsorbed layer works as the last protective
76 barrier before touching the collagenous cartilage tissue itself. The gel-like layer consists of a non-collagenous
77 proteoglycan layer (aggrecan, lubricin) acting as a low-shear layer. The overall lubrication performance is a result of
78 the adaptive multimode mechanism, in which a different mechanism takes turns or acts simultaneously based on
79 operating parameters. [18]

81 Hydrogel is a material resembling articular cartilage, composed of water and a solid phase. It retains and releases
82 water under deformation, crucial for effective lubrication. While cartilage comprises collagen and proteoglycan,
83 hydrogel consists of cross-linked polymer chains in water. Unlike solid surfaces, hydrogel's frictional behavior is rather
84 different, reaching low friction levels down to 0.0001. [26]

85 Gong et al. [26, 27] proposed a friction model for gels, depicting frictional stress dependence on sliding velocity. Two
86 hydrogel-to-substrate responses were outlined: repulsive and attractive. Repulsive friction involves hydrated water
87 polymer chains, with friction proportional to sliding velocity. Attractive friction comprises elastic friction at low speed

88 (as a result of adsorbing polymer chains), transitioning to hydrated lubrication at high speed. Poly(vinyl chloride alcohol)
89 (PVA) hydrogel has potential as artificial cartilage due to biocompatibility and stability. Initial studies in the 1990s
90 highlighted PVA's superior shock-absorbency but challenges in bone attachment. [28–30] Maintaining water content
91 similar to natural cartilage helps in reducing friction, but compromises strength and wear resistance. [31]

92 The performance of PVA hydrogel hinges greatly on cross-linking temperature conditions, influencing its
93 microstructure and overall behavior. Two common methods used are freeze-thawing (FT) and cast-drying (CD), yielding
94 different mechanical responses. [31] FT produces an opaque porous structure with high water content, enhancing
95 adsorbed film formation and lubrication properties. CD results in a transparent homogenous structure with lower
96 permeability. However, wear resistance remains a challenge. [32] Laminar FT on CD gel (LM) shows promise with
97 extremely low friction and wear. [33] Composite hydrogels (CP) combining FT and high/low-temperature drying
98 processes exhibit improved wear resistance and low friction. [34] Structural changes occur over time, impacting
99 permeability and lubrication. Aging leads to decreased permeability but also hardening, potentially limiting further
100 applications. [35] Despite advancements, hydrogels perform well only under mild conditions, highlighting the need for
101 further development for clinical use.

102 The lubrication mechanism of synovial cartilage is exceptional. Its understanding has major importance in
103 developing a material that would equally substitute cartilage and help numerous patients worldwide. Most recent studies
104 emphasize the importance of understanding lubrication at the molecular level. PVA hydrogel, as a potentially promising
105 material, still needs further improvement as its significant drawback remains its low strength. In this study, multiple
106 types of PVA hydrogel were examined for their performance in boundary lubrication to elucidate the behavior of close
107 contact lubrication. Based on the comprehensive experimental study and detailed surface evaluation a solid-to-solid
108 boundary lubrication was proposed, PVA hydrogel was sorted into two categories featuring its behavior, and the effect
109 of protein solution was observed in close contact lubrication.

111 2. Materials and methods

112 2.1 Materials

113 Five types of PVA hydrogels with identical chemical compositions were prepared for the frictional experiments,
114 **Figure 1.** Variations in overall physical properties (stiffness, porosity, microcrystalline structure) were driven by
115 controlled conditions in a heat-controlled chamber. All PVA hydrogels were prepared by freeze-thawing (FT) method
116 and cast-drying (CD) method. The preparation process of the PVA solution remains the same regardless of the type of

117 fabricated hydrogel. A 15 wt% aqueous solution of PVA (Polymerization degree: 1700, Saponification degree: 98-99
118 mol%, Kuraray Co., Ltd.) was used as a raw material.

119 PVA FT hydrogel was prepared with four repeated FT cycles, exposed to $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 8 hours followed by $4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$
120 for 16 hours in a single cycle. This results in a heterogenous opaque structure with low strength (as compared to the
121 following hydrogels), rough surface, and high permeability. PVA CD hydrogel was prepared by a single CD cycle at 60
122 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 80 \%RH . The structure is then homogeneous and transparent, resulting in higher strength, smooth surface, and
123 low permeability. Following PVA hydrogels are a combination of FT and CD methods. PVA CP hydrogel production
124 process consists of two FT and CD sets, where the first CD set is at high-temperature drying ($60\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 80 \%RH) and
125 the second at low-temperature ($8\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 50 \%RH). The methods were executed in this order FT-CD-FT-CD. The
126 duration of a high-temperature CD set is crucial for driving the CP resultant properties. For experimental purposes, two
127 CP hydrogels were made. CP24 had been left at a high-temperature CD set for 24 hours, CP06 for 6 hours. The
128 combination of the FT and CD method gives the CP hydrogel some unique properties otherwise found only on each
129 method separately. Additionally, FT/CD ($20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, 50 \%RH) laminar PVA hydrogel (PVA LM) was prepared. For
130 experimental purposes, CD (transparent) laminar layer was used as the friction surface. While other PVA hydrogels
131 were made of one PVA solution, LM hydrogel consisted of two such solutions to achieve the laminar structure.

132 **Figure 1:** Manufactured PVA hydrogels used in experiments: a) PVA FT, b) PVA CD, c) PVA LM, d) PVA CP06, e) PVA CP24 [36]

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133 2.2 Rheometer

134 The Rheometer MCR302 Anton Paar facilitates comprehensive rheological investigations, offering rotational
135 and oscillatory modes for analyzing flow behavior and structural properties of viscoelastic materials. This study aimed
136 to elucidate the boundary lubrication effect of PVA hydrogels, as a potential artificial cartilage replacement, across
137 various sliding velocities. The employed contact configuration was a ball-on-plate. Preloading hydrogels 30 minutes
138 before friction tests mitigated fluid-induced low friction, and allowing solid-solid interaction dominance, **Figure 2A**.

139 Experimental procedures involved clamping three PVA specimens, immersing them in lubricant, establishing contact
140 with a glass specimen, and applying a predetermined normal force for 30 minutes. Unloading for 10 seconds allows
141 quick rehydration before reapplying the normal force for 60 seconds. Friction tests were run under constant normal load,
142 provided by a spinning steel shaft with an attached glass ball, **Figure 2B-C**.

143 Experiments, (see Table 1) were conducted under 5 N and 10 N normal loads using PBS lubricant, and under
144 5 N in protein solution. Velocity ranged from 0.00001 mm/s to 1000 mm/s. Specimens (6 x 10 mm) varied in thickness
145 (CD: 1 mm, FT: 2 mm, CP06: 2.5 mm, CP24: 1 mm, LM: 3.5 mm) based on drying process parameters. Cyanoacrylate
146 adhesive affixed PVA specimens to polycarbonate plates. The glass ball (diameter: 12.8 mm) served as a sliding
147 counterpart. Experiments were maintained at 25 °C temperature.

148 Three series of experiments (1 series = 3 samples, Figure 2) underwent three repetitions, totaling nine frictional
149 results per configuration. The three initial frictional results were discarded due to specimen run-in phases. Subsequent
150 results were averaged for further analysis. Frictional behavior is thus the average of six frictional responses noted in the
151 plot as Average 2-3, see **Figure 2D**.

Figure 2: A-left: (1) Illustration of friction behavior on time after applying load, A-right: (1) initially low friction is conducted by fluid phase leaking out of the hydrated gel, (2) after the exhaustion of interstitial fluid solid-solid contact becomes dominant resulting in friction increase and gradual COF stabilization. B) Experimental procedure for measuring friction using the rheometer. Each of the 3 series was 3 times repeated. C) A schema of the rheometer experimental configuration. D) An example of two frictional experimental configurations on one PVA hydrogel type. The bottom curve is a result of the 0-max speed range (from 0 mm/s to 1000 mm/s), the curve above is a result of the max-0 speed range (from 1000 mm/s to 0 mm/s). The lines Test 2 and Test 3 are the experimental results of three series, and Average 2-3 is the average of those experimental results. [36]

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Tested specimens	PVA hydrogel	FT	CD	LM	CP24	CP06
	Fabrication process	FT	CD	Laminar FT/CD	FT-CD-FT-CD	FT-CD-FT-CD
	Thickness [mm]	2	1	3.5	1	2.5
	Water content [%]	~85	~75	~73	~60	~73
Experimental configuration	Ball material	Glass, ø12.8 mm				
	Plate material	FT, CD, LM, CP24, CP06				
	Speed range [mm/s]	(0.00001, 1000) and (1000, 0.00001)				
	Lubricants	PBS, protein solution (1.4 wt% albumin, 0.7 wt% γ -globulin)				
	Temperature	25 °C				
	Normal load	5 N, 10 N				

2.3 Laser microscope

The Keyence VK-X260K laser scanning microscope enables precise non-contact measurement and analysis of surface topography, including 3D profiles and roughness parameters. In this study, the laser microscope was employed to observe PVA hydrogel surfaces, providing background for data from friction experiments. Both worn-out and virgin specimens were observed. The virgin specimens served for reference. Multiple images were captured for each surface, focusing on different locations. Surface parameters were measured predominantly at the central area, see **Figure 3**. Each experiment series yielded 9 worn-out specimens, of which 5 were selected for observation.

Figure 3: A) The image setup taken for every tested PVA hydrogel. B) A "C" central surface image, surface profile, and roughness. [36]

2.4 Viscoelasticity experiments

The viscoelasticity properties of tested hydrogel specimens were conducted on the same device (Rheometer MCR302 Anton Paar) and experimental configuration as in friction experiments, Figure 2C. The only difference laid in experimental procedures changing a parameter, Figure 2B. Creep deformation was kept for 15 min at 2 N, static load for 1 min at 2 N. Unloading and rehydration was unchanged. For each PVA specimen a strain distribution dependence (range: 0.01 to 1000 %) under constant frequency (1 Hz) and normal force (2 N) was obtained. Each series was repeated twice.

3 Results

The frictional results of PVA hydrogels with different preparation processes have been tested on ball-on-disc (glass on hydrogel) configuration, shown in **Figure 2**. Each hydrogel underwent three experimental setups: 5 N normal

174 load with PBS lubricant, 10 N with PBS, and 5 N with protein solution. Over the entire experiment, several common
175 phenomena could be seen.

176 **Figure 4** shows how COF changed over the speed range. COF was measured at gradual acceleration (0-max)
177 and deceleration (max-0) from static load (“0”) to a speed of 1000 mm/s (“max”). Throughout the acceleration, COF is
178 steeply increasing at low speeds reaching its maximum at 10-30 mm/s, then falling to its minimum values at high speeds.
179 During deceleration, COF reached significantly lower maximum values than at acceleration. COF at max-0 increased
180 until 2-10 mm/s, then mildly decreased at a low-speed range. Besides the maximum peak of COF, named 2nd transition
181 point (2nd TP) related to a transition of lubrication regime, an irregular change of COF could be seen in some results at
182 low-speed range ($10^{-4} - 10^{-5}$ mm/s), named as 1st transition point (1st TP). The exact values of transition points are
183 recorded in Table 2, where 1st TP is understood as an inflex point, and 2nd TP as the maximum value.

184 The tested PVA hydrogels could be sorted into two categories: soft hydrogels and hard hydrogels. Hydrogels
185 whose dominant preparation process was the FT method are listed as soft hydrogels: FT, CP06, and LM hydrogels. Hard
186 hydrogels are listed as CD and CP06, which dominant process was the CD method. Specimens in each category exhibit
187 similar fundamental behavior, such as transition areas, COF, and stiffness. Unlike hard hydrogels, soft gels exhibit
188 higher COF, and transition points are located at higher velocities.

189 Considering lubricants and the load used in the experiments, each component further influences the overall
190 COF-velocity dependence of a tested hydrogel type. As seen in **Figure 4**, protein solution lifts-up the COF at all types
191 of hydrogels and keeps COF notably higher than PBS lubricant does. Observing the results, a higher load (10 N) usually
192 stands for lower, or nearly equal COF compared to 5 N at a low-velocity range. An exception here is FT and LM gel.
193 FT gel is, unlike other hydrogels, a very soft material exhibiting heavy plastic deformation. The results of LM gel have
194 higher data variance, compared to other hydrogels.

195 The influence of lubricants and load on TPs is also visible. Regarding the 1st TP, located at low speed, protein
196 lubricant notably prolonged the area before the TP, and exceeded PBS. Importantly, 1st TP seems to be influenced by a
197 category of hydrogel to a great extent. Soft hydrogel has 1st TP about an order of magnitude higher than hard hydrogel,
198 see Table 2. While acceleration, at 2nd TP it could be noticed, that specimens with protein lubricant reached maximum
199 COF as first, followed by PBS. On the contrary, while deceleration, COF peak (2nd TP) was reached sooner with PBS
200 than with protein lubricant.

201 Considering the influence of the load. Higher load seems to shift the 1st TP to slightly lower velocities and shifts
202 to higher velocities at the 2nd TP than lower load at acceleration. During deceleration, maximum COF is achieved by

203 the high load first. In other words, a higher load might be less sensitive to lubrication regime change at high-speed
204 acceleration than at deceleration. A higher load at 1st TP, located at boundary lubrication, might accelerate a change
205 happening in this area.

206 Besides COF data, **Figure 4** contains a frictional force at selected velocities (0.1, 1, 10, 100 mm/s). Similarly,
207 as in COF, a common behavior could have been observed, matching the transition points, and copying the COF-velocity
208 curve shape trend. At low speed, friction force was the highest when using protein lubricant, subsequently for PBS 10
209 N and 5 N normal load. Concerning COF, friction force increases up until the maximum COF (2nd T.P), here the friction
210 force of 10 N normal load becomes by far the highest for all samples. Beyond the peak point, the friction force is falling
211 to low values. It is also worth noting that friction force magnitude for acceleration is much higher than for deceleration
212 experiments.

Figure 4: Averaged frictional experimental data of tested PVA hydrogels. At velocities of 0.01, 1, 10, and 100 mm/s a frictional force is indicated. [36]

		10^{-4} mm/s			10^{-5} mm/s		
		FT	CP06	LM	CD	CP24	
0-max	1st TP	PBS, 5 N	2.1	4.1	1	0	2.5
		PBS, 10 N	2.1	1.3	2	0	0
		Protein, 5 N	17	10	8.3	8.1	6.5
	2nd TP	PBS, 5 N	38.2	38.2	12.0	7.5	9.4
		PBS, 10 N	30.3	38.2	24.0	15.0	15.0
		Protein, 5 N	19.0	19.0	12.0	5.9	4.7
max-0	2nd TP	PBS, 5 N	24.0	11.9	7.5	2.3	2.3
		PBS, 10 N	9.4	15.0	9.4	2.9	4.7
		Protein, 5 N	3.7	0.2	0.1	0.9	0.7

Table 2: Transition points (TPs) of COF-mm/s curve. 1st TP (inflex point), 2nd TP (maximum value)

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Subsequently, an image of tested specimens was taken, and the profile was evaluated, see **Figure 5** and **Figure 6**. Browsing through the images, some specimens are scratched/worn out more than others. CD and CP24 hydrogels belonging to the hard hydrogel category and are visibly scratched, unlike the soft FT, CP06, and LM hydrogel. Moreover, hard hydrogels subjected to deceleration (max-0) experiments have notably more visible scratches and rougher surfaces than specimens after the acceleration friction test (0-max). Soft hydrogels show much less scratched surface, at some samples contact surface could not be found at all. No clear difference is seen at soft hydrogels to distinguish 0-max or max-0 subjected surface. Even though hard hydrogel has significant wear after the friction test, roughness remains lower than for soft hydrogels. Profile parameters such as roughness and waviness are primarily driven by fabricating processes, as indicated in reference images.

Considering viscoelastic properties, only a result with strain distribution were evaluated, see **Figure 11**. It could be seen that storage modulus (G') of all PVA hydrogels is higher value at lower shear strain region than viscous modulus (G''). G'' becomes dominant at higher shear after reaching cross-over point. The magnitude of G' and G'' is observed to be at the highest for PVA CD. With decreasing order, the PVA specimens are sorted for their G' , G'' value as follows: CD, CP24, CP06, LM, FT – where PVA FT exhibited by far the lowest G' , G'' modulus value. The cross-over points sorted from the lowest shear strain to the highest are as follows: LM, CP06, CP24, CD, FT, Other than PVA FT, specimens are grouped together, whereas the FT has its cross-over point further at 100 % shear strain.

Figure 5: Laser microscope images of tested PVA hydrogel samples (reference, FT, CD). [36]

Figure 6: Laser microscope images of tested PVA hydrogel samples (CP06, CP24, LM). [36]

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232 4. Discussion

233 4.1 An overview

234 The present study introduces a comparison of various types of PVA hydrogels prepared by a combination of FT
 235 and CD methods. The study is based on the findings made by Yarimitsu, and Murakami [33, 34, 37] – clearly indicating
 236 that PVA is an exceptional material worth to consider in the search for artificial cartilage. Friction investigation was
 237 utilized with regards to biphasic lubrication reduction [10] so the effect of boundary lubrication active after long

238 continuous loading is revealed. The course of COF data measured at different velocities is strikingly similar to the
239 repulsive-adhesive friction model of gels proposed by Gong et al. [26], discussing a behavior difference between solid
240 materials and polymer-made hydrogels.

241 The present study aims to replicate the repulsion-adhesion model, evaluate the boundary lubrication. Based on
242 the experiments, select a hydrogel that performed the best, and highlight the desired properties that should be considered
243 when developing artificial cartilage.

244 **4.2 Lubrication regimes**

245 Based on the frictional result observation a common course of the friction curve has been outlined in **Figure 7A**.
246 Two outlying areas with low COF have been identified. As Gong et al. [26] suggested, low-speed frictional stress is
247 primarily a result of the adsorption of polymer molecules having enough time to absorb on surfaces, whereas at higher
248 velocity this adsorption ability is lost and is replaced by fluid film lubrication. Studying the performed experiments, it
249 could be noticed COF curve is composed of concave and convex shapes. Convex shapes are assigned to lubrication
250 regimes, concave to the transition between those regimes.

251 Starting with acceleration (0-max), low-speed friction is allocated with static adhesion (SA), referring to **Figure**
252 **10**, discussed later. With a slight increase in speed, the experiment shifts to dynamic adhesion (DA). The time for
253 adhesion is limited and fluid load support is too weak to separate the surfaces, this is accompanied by a significant COF
254 increase. It is believed DA causes most of the wear during friction test. As the speed increases, fluid load support
255 becomes stronger leading to a stop in COF growth and ultimate steep fall after EHL is fully established.

256 Observing the deceleration case (max-0), the situation is rather different. From the initial high speed, sustaining
257 the EHL regime, and keeping the COF low, friction does not follow the same steep growth pattern. EHL remains active
258 for a significantly wider speed range, accompanied by only a small COF increase as the speed decreases. The lubrication
259 regime is then changed with decreasing velocity to DA and COF continues in gradual decline. At almost static movement,
260 the SA was not realized. Due to that, and due to wear, the COF does not reach back to zero values as it does in the 0-max
261 case. The exact course and shape of the curve are further influenced by PVA hydrogels, lubricants, and load, influencing
262 primarily TPs and adhesion capabilities.

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264 The authors illustrate the friction mechanism behavior in **Figure 7B**. At almost none or small movement,
265 polymer chains of a hydrogel adhere on opposing glass ball. If a small movement is initiated, polymers stretch. Stretched
266 polymers hinder direct body contact and give time for other polymers to adhere, then they elastically break and adhere

267 again. Due to the higher speed at DA, polymer adhesion becomes limited and body wear is allowed, resulting in wear
 268 and COF steep increase. With increasing speed at the DA region, a portion of EHL gradually takes dominance, after
 269 which COF sharply falls to a small value.

270 As deceleration (max-0) COF does not rise to acceleration COF values, it is suggested that the mechanism might
 271 lie in EHL-induced rehydration, earlier proposed by Moore et al. [17]. The induced rehydration is due to a high pressure
 272 within the contact where the lubricant is forced inside the hydrogel's matrix. This partial rehydration is believed to
 273 evoke interstitial fluid load support at lower velocities and partially separate opposing surfaces at the DA region.

Figure 7: A) Observed COF-velocity shape behavior. B) Proposal of boundary lubrication mechanism. Note: The grey ellipses represent elastic strain caused by direct body interaction.

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275 4.3 Summary and general properties found at PVA specimens.

276 As taken images showed, PVA hydrogels fabricated dominantly at low temperatures exhibited significantly
 277 smaller damage than hard hydrogels fabricated at higher temperatures. Although the profile parameters are much
 278 smoother at hard hydrogels, it seems to not be an issue driving the wear resistance. What is interesting is the fact that in
 279 the deceleration (max-0) friction test, the surface damage was greater than for acceleration (0-max). This raises a

280 question of what the exact mechanism behind that might be. The summary Table 3 shows us that the parameters (COF,
281 F_T , Ra) usually pointing at surface damage are higher in soft hydrogels than in hard cases. The key to resolving this
282 seems to lie in adhesion and rigidity. The authors suggest that material properties effectively working at biphasic
283 lubrication, such as limited permeability, and smooth and rigid surface may not perform well at close contact boundary
284 level. Adhesion capabilities and rehydration of these hydrogels are then fairly limited resulting in body contact and wear.
285 More desired would be to have a softer hydrogel, which would be elastically deformed and stretched by countersurface
286 roughness, but not torn and allowed partial water rehydration at EHL. Such criteria highlight CP06 hydrogel with
287 improved PVA adhesion.

288 **Figure 9A** and Table 3 compares hard-soft hydrogel behavior. The scheme indicates that soft hydrogel operates
289 at higher friction over the whole speed range and has its TPs at notably higher velocities than hard hydrogel. **Figure 9B**
290 and Table 4 describes an average observed influence of load and lubricants on COF. The positions of TPs are driven by
291 the adhesion capability of the overall friction interface, as seen in Table 2. Using PBS lubricant adhesion is considered
292 only PVA-made. The protein solution was reported to form an additional laminar protein protective layer. [22, 38] In
293 this study the protein solution forming a adsorbed layers was expected to reduce the surface damage, as some studies
294 suggested under a proposed composition (1.4 wt% albumin + 0.7 wt% γ -globulin) [22, 24]. However, the experimental
295 results show similar or slightly worse damage done to the surface than in the case of PBS. Although the overall adhesion
296 using protein has risen, it does not seem to promote the adhesion type needed for better surface protection. Moreover,
297 due to a lack of biphasic lubrication separating the surface on a larger scale, the protective protein layer may not form
298 at all. Thus, protein in the experiments may only result in friction increase due to dispersed protein agglomerates.

Figure 8: A proposed structure of PVA hydrogel samples. Protruding PVA polymers promoting adhesion create from tangled inhomogeneous structure. Rigid structure has more tight-stretched PVA polymers linked to micro-crystallites (MC). PVA FT (4x FT cycle), PVA CD (60 °C, 80 %RH), PVA CP24 (60 °C, 80 %RH) *, PVA CP06 (8 °C, 50 %RH) *, PVA LM (20 °C, 50 %RH) **. *high-temperature drying cycle, **CD cycle

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300 As already mentioned, CP06 gel has shown the lowest wear damage. By simply observing the taken images It
 301 could be noticed that LM gel exhibits very low wear damage as well. LM gel has, unlike CP06, a superficial layer made
 302 of hard CD. This seemingly disturbs the proposed idea that smooth and rigid surfaces do not perform well at the
 303 boundary level. **Figure 8** proposes structures of tested hydrogels. PVA FT is fabricated at low temperatures (-20°C, 4°C)
 304 resulting in opaque, soft, and inhomogeneous structures containing small microcrystalline. On the other hand, PVA CD
 305 (60 °C) is glass transparent, rigid, homogenous, and contains large microcrystals. Neither of those two have shown
 306 satisfactory results. PVA FT was heavily plastically deformed resulting in significant friction force, **Figure 9C**. Although
 307 PVA CD deformation was elastic, wear damage is undeniable. Combining both fabricating methods we obtained CP
 308 and LM hydrogels. Unlike PVA FT, CP24 has a less tangled and more tight-stretched polymer structure with large-
 309 dispersed microcrystals formed by a high-temperature drying process. Tribological behavior is similar to CD gel. CP06
 310 has more tangled polymer structure than CP24, that is due to limited time exposure at high temperatures, where also
 311 microcrystals grow smaller. Such a structure seems to be close enough to retain FT properties and at the same time
 312 obtain decent toughness from the CD process. PVA LM hydrogel consists of two layers – FT on the bottom, and CD on
 313 top. Although, the top layer consists of a thin CD layer, adhesion, as well as other tribological results, classify LM as a
 314 soft hydrogel, rather than a hard hydrogel. Possibly because the upper CD layer was made at lower temperatures than
 315 simple PVA CD. Additionally, LM gel has significantly better contact conformity and better contact pressure
 316 distribution due to its higher thickness. Furthermore, Yarimitsu et al. [39] indicated that LM gel might develop an
 317 additional low-shear thin superficial layer consisted of protruding PVA molecules made during the swollen process.

318 The protruding PVA molecules in PVA LM may similarly as in PVA CP06 adhere onto the countersurface providing
 319 boundary surface separation.

320 The amount of protruding PVA molecules might play an important role in the overall adhesion capability of a
 321 hydrogel. Soft hydrogel with an inhomogeneous or irregular polymer structure is expected to have more dangling
 322 polymer chains capable of adhering to opposing surfaces than hard hydrogel with homogenous crosslinking, **Figure 8**.
 323 Microcrystalline typically forms a cross-linking bonding point for PVA molecular chains. [40] If the hydrogel is an FT-
 324 like structure and bonding is not uniform, mechanical properties are poor. More uniform displacement of
 325 microcrystalline (CD, CPs) thus results in enhanced mechanical strength. If micro-crystallites grew larger, additional
 326 stiffening is enhanced. PVA molecular chains also drive water-absorbing capacity. If PVA chains are tied up too much
 327 with cross-linking, water content, and swelling ratio is reduced.

328 **Figure 9:** An observed general behaviors of A) hard and soft PVA hydrogel, B) load (5 N, 10 N) and lubricants (PBS, protein), C) friction force
 329 (F_T), D) Observed PVA surface damage after friction test.

328
 329 Displaying both axes of frictional results in logarithmic scale, a couple of interesting aspects will appear, as can
 330 be seen in Figure 10. Most importantly it is observed that the region of static adhesion has a linear dependence. This
 331 evokes an idea of finding a decent mathematical formulation. Looking at solid mechanics, an equation related to elastic
 332 behavior is strain energy written as (1).

$$\text{strain energy} = \frac{1}{2} E \cdot \epsilon^2 \quad (1)$$

333

334 where E stands for elastic modulus and ϵ for strain.

335 Based on that, we could quantify the relative differences in toughness for each hydrogel. PVA FT has the lowest
 336 gradient indicating a very soft structure. PVA CD and CP24 on the other hand have almost vertical gradient suggesting
 337 its high stiffness. CP06 and LM gel exhibit in middle gradient value, **Figure 10**. It is also fair to note that in the region
 338 where hard gels have very steep gradients, only have only a few data points taken, therefore the accuracy is not precise.
 339 The region of DA appears to be close to a linear course as well. Protein lubricant and soft hydrogel promote DA linearity.
 340 Hard hydrogels and PBS lubricants have rather concave courses. We know friction consists of adhesive and a ploughing
 341 component (2), (3), (4).

$$\mu_{\text{total}} = \mu_{\text{adhesive}} + \mu_{\text{ploughing}} \quad (2)$$

$$\mu_{\text{adhesive}} = \tau_y \cdot A_r / F_N \quad (3)$$

$$\mu_{\text{ploughing}} = F_P / F_N \quad (4)$$

342

343 where τ_y stands for shear yield strength, A_r for estimated total real contact area, F_P for ploughing force, F_N for normal
 344 force.

345 It is suggested that the DA region with linear friction has a dominant adhesive component, and the concave-shaped
 346 course is attributed to ploughing friction. Such explanation corresponds with observed worn-out samples. Soft hydrogels
 347 have less scratched surface than hard hydrogels, where the adhesion is believed to be limited. For summery of those
 348 findings see, Table 5.

349 Further on, based on the measured viscoelastic properties, **Figure 11**, we see that solid interface plays a more
 350 dominant role in boundary lubrication than interstitial fluid. Due to hard hydrogel's low permeability, a higher amount
 351 of water is kept within the matrix relative to soft hydrogels after 30 min static loading. G' attributed to elastic modulus
 352 is consistent with the adhesion gradient in the SA region in **Figure 10** – the steeper the adhesion gradient, the tougher
 353 and less adhesive the PVA hydrogel is. Looking at the cross-sections of G' and G'' , we could see that additional fluid
 354 load support might be evoked if hydrogel is strained beyond tested conditions (G'' becomes dominant). PVA FT however
 355 need to be 100 % strained to evoke dominance of G'' . Excessive stain surely leads to irreversible plastic deformation,
 356 which PVA FT already exceeded at experiments. Operated conditions were believed to be in a matter of units of percent
 357 for CD, CPs, and LM. For PVA FT the strain was likely in the tens of percent. This second-fluid load support might

358 work as fail-safe mechanism when overloading the cartilage, further highlighting the PVA CP06 and PVA LM, having
 359 their cross-section points at lower strain percentage.

Figure 10: An observed COF behavior showed at logarithmic scale.

360

Figure 11: Viscoelastic behavior of PVA hydrogel samples. [36]

361

	● PVA Soft		● PVA Hard	Note:
Wear	0-max ~ max-0	<	0-max < max-0	Wear tracks are significant in hard PVA.
COF, Ft [N]	0-max >> max-0	≥	0-max >> max-0	Soft PVA has higher COF over the SA and DA region.
Ra, Rz	0-max ~ max-0	>	0-max ≤ max-0	Roughness is greater in soft PVA.
Adhesion	● higher	>	● lower	TPs of soft PVA are shifted to higher velocity than PVA hard.
Friction	Adhesive		Ploughing	Dominant friction component in PVA samples.

362

Table 3: A comparison of soft and hard PVA hydrogels based on the observation. The table is related to Figure 9.

	● PBS, 5 N	● PBS, 10 N	● Protein, 5 N	
SA	=	=	higher	SA is almost equal in PBS, in protein solution SA is clearly higher.
TPs (1st)	middle	lower	higher	The higher the load in PBS, the lower the SA. Protein always increases SA.
TPs (2nd)	middle	higher	lower	Higher load suppress the EHD. Protein's viscosity helps EHD to build-up.
COF	middle	lower	higher	Considering SA, DA region.
Ft [N]	lower	middle	higher	Considering SA, DA region. At max. COF 10 N load causes higher FT at COF peak.

Table 4: A comparison of lubricants and loads on the observation. The table is related to Figure 9.

	PVA FT	PVA CP06	PVA LM		PVA CD	PVA CP24
Ra	0-max	1.64 – 2.35	1.17 – 1.29	1.12 – 1.57	0.35 – 0.42	0.32 – 0.50
	max-0	1.60 – 2.43	1.04 – 1.35	1.20 – 1.38	0.70 – 0.79	0.43 – 0.80
Wear	plastic deformation	small	small		high	high
Rigidity	soft	middle	middle		tough	tough
Adhesion	good	good	good	>	poor	poor
Friction	Adhesive	Adhesive	Adhesive		Ploughing	Ploughing
	Soft PVA TPs are located within the 10^{-4} order velocity. The inclination of SA is similar.				Hard PVA TPs are located within the 10^{-5} order velocity. The inclination of SA is similar.	

Table 5: A comparison of tested PVA samples on the observation and the authors assumptions.

5. Conclusion

The present study has introduced a tribological comparison of five PVA hydrogel specimens with different physiological properties. The friction experiments were conducted with diminished interstitial fluid load support allowing a focus on solid-to-solid interactions. A boundary lubrication mechanism considering PVA adhesion was proposed.

The experiments highlighted the importance of balanced proportion of PVA polymer adhesion ability (for reducing ploughing friction), decent conformity, and EHL induced rehydration. These properties are driven by preparation processes defining the cross-linking structure.

- Too soft hydrogel (PVA FT) enhances adhesion and permeability but cannot resist mechanical stress.
- Stiff hydrogel (PVA CD, PVA CP24) may perform well at biphasic lubrication (long-last interstitial fluid load support). However, at body contact is easy to be worn by roughness.

- 377 ▪ PVA CP06 and PVA LM hydrogel indicated a minimum wear damage. That is due to reasonable rigidity
378 allowing rather elastic than plastic ploughing. Promoted PVA polymer adhesion further reduced abrasive wear
379 by wrapping the asperities of the opposite surface providing additional surface separation.
- 380 ▪ Protein molecules (γ -globulin, albumin) did not show any protective effect of the surface. It is believed a certain
381 protective film is formed at biphasic lubrication. However, at permanent boundary lubrication the protein film
382 is disrupted and loses the protective effect. Furthermore, the disrupted film clusters may wrap-up the protruding
383 PVA chains and reduce wear resistance.

384

385 A subsequent study may focus on verifying the proposed boundary lubrication mechanism, the description of
386 linking the protruding PVA with other SF constituents – namely HA and phospholipids. PVA chains might potentially
387 enhance cohesion between synovial molecules and solid boundary. This would help with developing a material with
388 superlubricity property.

389

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393

394 **Author's contributions**

395 M. Vrbka, D. Nečas, conceived the idea. D. Nečas, D. Němeček, H. Shinmori and S. Yarimitsu designed, performed
396 and analyzed the experiments. D. Němeček wrote the original draft of the manuscript. D. Nečas, Y. Sawae, I. Křupka
397 and M. Hartl supervised the study. All the authors provided suggestions for the final discussions, reviewed, edited and
398 read the manuscript and approved the final version.

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